

Capacocha

also known as “Qhapaq Hucha”

By Ryan Hechler, Tulane University

Entry tags: Religious Group, South American Religions, Abrahamic, Prehistoric South American Religions, Andes, Language, Quechuan, Quechua II, Quechua IIC, Inkas

The Capacocha (Qhapaq Hucha) ritual was a rite of sacrifice in which an imperial subject (biological male or female, ranging in age from childhood to young adulthood) of the Inka Empire (i.e., Tawantinsuyu) was selected based upon perceived "physical perfection." The selected individual would live like an Inka royal elite for a year prior to their sacrifice to Inti, the Sun God and patron deity of Tawantinsuyu. The act of sacrifice was typically completed on an important summit. Thus far, archaeological examples of the Capacocha ritual are limited to the southern portion of the Inka Empire within province of Qullasuyu.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 1532 CE

Region: Capacocha Sites in the Southern Andes

Region tags: Peru, South America, Chile, Bolivia, Peru, Andes, Argentina, Bolivia (Plurinational State of), Argentina, Chile, Southern Andes, Ecuador

Capacochas have been archaeologically documented throughout the southern Andes in the modern countries of Peru, Bolivia, Chile, and Argentina.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Enclosed?

– Yes

Notes: This ritual takes place over the course of the year. The selected individual to be sacrificed does partake in religious rituals and elite social events within enclosed spaces throughout the course of this year.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Elevated?

– Yes

Notes: The actual act of sacrifice typically takes place on a high summit of an important mountain or volcano.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ By a body of water?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: Sacred mountains were often venerated by the Inka as being a wak'a (objects/landscape features that were worshipped)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Specify: The final site of sacrifice is typically a mountainous summit, however the individual selected for sacrifice is prepared for a year living as an Inka elite, even if they are not ethnically Inka. Thus, this individual could be highly mobile in upper strata of Inka imperial society for the year prior to their sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– No

Notes: The final act of sacrifice occurs on a summit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– No

Notes: While the individual would certainly be in public contexts as a high profile selection for sacrifice, the final act of sacrifice is isolated from the general public.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: Typically on a high elevation point, an important summit of a mountain or volcano.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There can be mini structures built to house the respective qhapaq hucha, but these are minimal and typically made of stone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Typically in proximation to important peaks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: The individual picked for sacrifice would go through a year-long process of ritual grooming prior to sacrifice. There are various qhapaq hucha that were picked throughout the Inka Empire.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Daily:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Weekly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Seasonally:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Special events/occasions:

– Yes

Notes: The timing of the sacrifice itself could coincide with an important religious or political event.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 8760

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– Specify: Childhood to Late Teenage Years

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– No

Notes: While one's genetic background is not important, as any imperial subject of any socio-economic background could be in theory selected for this ritual, the selected individual is supposed to embrace some Inka notion of "physical perfection" and "social purity."

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– No

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: This is where the divide between ethnohistory and archaeology is currently -- the Spanish colonial chronicles would seem to indicate any ethnic group could become a capacocha, however the archaeological evidence has thus far only indicated individuals that are likely local to their southern Andean regions and are very likely not ethnically Inka. If the latter pattern is true, this would imply this was a monumental imperial social control approach.

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: The individual chosen to be a capacocha essentially grows into a life of elite comfort before sacrifice.

- ↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?
(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)
 - Age: Adults are not allowed to be selected.

- ↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they deceased humans:
 - No

 - ↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:
 - No

 - ↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:
 - No

 - ↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they high gods:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:
 - No

 - ↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:
Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to

change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: Socially coerced participants are the entirety of the community the individual is derived from.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Non-binary:
– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Other:
– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?
– N/A

Notes: The age is the entire range of the community and the respective Inka elites and religious specialists involved throughout the duration of the selected offering's remainder of life.

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?
– Yes

Notes: Adoration of the individual selected for sacrifice.

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?
– Yes

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?
– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Mummified ancestors are likely involved as the deceased were never truly due in many Andean cultures.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

Notes: The ceremony was specifically centered around generating a human offering to Inti, the Sun God and patron deity of the Inka Empire. Thus, some notion of Inti's satisfaction is involved.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

Notes: The individual selected for sacrifice does transform socially and spiritually when undergoing capacocha.

- ↳ Others:
 - No

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: This honestly depends on the definition of "spectator." The ultimate moment of sacrifice of the individual is done in a secluded location on a mountain peak with a religious specialist, however the many months leading up to this the individual is involved in high profile events with the Inka empire and its elites, however these events are not necessarily focused around them.

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is participation obligatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Consequences of non-participation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Social ostracism

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Status loss

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Material/Physical punishment

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Supernatural punishment

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Other

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: Maintaining spiritual balance -- through the appeasement of Inti, the Sun God, agricultural fertility can be maintained, political calamity avoided, and natural disasters potentially mitigated.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– No

Notes: Less about "change," more about "stability" and guaranteeing the functioning "status quo."

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

Notes: The capacocha offering is transformed in a number of senses.

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ For deceased humans:

– No

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: This is perhaps an aspect, but part of a largest sense of cosmic balance.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: Yes, but not in the sense conveyed in the options above. The self-transformation is the individual being selected for offering to cross over to the spiritual plane as a "pure" sacrifice. They transform through death, but are not the "living dead" like mummified ancestors and their political participations in local communities in the empire.

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?
 - No
- ↳ Is this a naming ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?
 - No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

↳ As part of a celebration:

– No

↳ For love:

– No

↳ For social coordination:

– No

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– No

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:

– Yes

↳ Further ritual checks:

– Yes

Notes: Capacochas were constantly selected.

↳ Other:

– N/A

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

–Specify: 2

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves kneeling:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves prostrating:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve remaining immobile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ What is the distance covered (in kilometers)?

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are individuals close to one another?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there physical contact between individuals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve touch?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve holding hands?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve linking arms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve embracing?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve kissing?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve sexual contact?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they totems:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they religious icons:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they vessels:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they masks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is water used?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is earth used?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is fire used?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it touched?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it worn?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– Specify: 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is food consumed?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a type of alcoholic drink?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it naturally fermented:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it distilled:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a stimulant?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it modern tobacco:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it pre-modern tobacco:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it caffeine:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it betel nut:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it khat:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it coca:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it contain cacao?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it contain kava?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it cannabis or cannabinoid?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it opium?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it MDMA?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a psychedelic?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it smoked:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it ingested:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Alone:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ With food:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ With liquid:

–Yes [specify]: Chicha

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it applied topically:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it chewed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a suppository:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it snorted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it injected:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it offered into the fire:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does the individual retain biographical identity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does the individual retain control of the body?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does a spirit possession take place?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it cause the individual to speak in an incomprehensible language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it generate super-strength?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it lead to a prophecy/clairvoyance?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it create an extra-human resilience/resistance to harm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it help an individual to gain other new abilities or properties?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve spirit travel?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is the individual chosen (e.g., by a supernatural agent)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there a method of induction?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is there a substitution used to represent the symbolic offerings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are animals offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are humans offered?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Do individuals offer themselves?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are adults offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are children offered?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they male:

– Yes: 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they female:

– Yes: 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they transgender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they non-binary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they enslaved persons or from another vulnerable sector of society?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the individuals offered from within the community?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the individuals offered from outside the community?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the individuals offered as a whole?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are specific parts of the individuals offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are the individuals offered war captives or war spoils?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are commodities offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are household items offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are personal items offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is clothing offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are musical instrument offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are texts offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are weapons offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they self-imposed?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Are they other-imposed?

– Yes

Notes: The imperial subject selected for sacrifice is quite literally murdered by a ritual specialist.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve sensory deprivation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve submersion in water?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve being in a difficult bodily position?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve the consumption of disgusting substances?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve sleep deprivation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve physical exhaustion?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve physical discomfort?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it environmental:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a discomfort due to specific clothing:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Is it a surface discomfort:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve excessive labor?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve psychological discomfort?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves terror:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves humiliation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves isolation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves a taboo violation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve physical pain?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves piercing(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves fire:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves beating:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves flagellation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves cutting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ It involves abrasion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve the consumption of painful substances:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve positive emotion?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve negative emotion?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve breath manipulation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve a vow of silence?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve the subversion of social categories?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve non-normative sexual acts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve celibacy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– No

Notes: This ritual can coincide with other rituals. The selected sacrifice can partake in high profile imperial rituals until their ultimate sacrifice a year after selection.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– Yes

Notes: This ritual can coincide with other rituals. The selected sacrifice can partake in high profile imperial rituals until their ultimate sacrifice a year after selection.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Low

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– High

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– Low

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity

– High

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

–Specify: 8760

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Vertical

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

– Through social imitation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

– Religious specialists

– Political leader(s)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Capacochas Sites in the Southern Andes

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